

TOURISM VILLAGE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM BASED ON STAKEHOLDER COLLABORATION: CASE STUDY OF JATILUWIH TOURISM VILLAGE IN BALI

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ABSTRACT

Jatiluwh Tourism Village management system based on collaboration between stakeholders is a study for the development of tourism villages in Bali. This research using a qualitative descriptive method supported by data obtained through in-depth interviews with informants and also direct observation to tourist villages. Data were analysed using participation theory. The analysis shows that the management system of the Jatiluwh tourist village which is one of the cultural heritages that has been established by **United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization** (UNESCO) more concern into stakeholder involvement. It is the most important element in the development of Jatiluwh village as tourist destinations. The implication of this research for the tourism industry is that advanced tourist destinations must still prioritize good collaboration for sustainability.

Keywords: Jatiluwh, management system, collaboration, tourism village.

1. INTRODUCTION

Villages are currently one of the current tourism assets in Indonesia, because a village that has a unique culture, tradition, and abundant natural resources is one of the attractions that can attract tourists to come and visit. According to Sudibya (2018) tourism villages are one of the tourism assets based on the potentials owned by a village which are developed as tourism products that can attract tourists to visit. A tourist village is a village managed by the government or village community to be developed into a tourist destination which can later become a source of income for the village so that with the existence of the tourism village, it is hoped that it will be able to improve the welfare of the existing community.

Indonesia currently has a lot of tourist villages that are still being developed into tourist destinations for the Indonesian state. Bali is one of them, Bali is a destination for tourists who come to Indonesia. Bali has a million beauties attraction that cannot be explored in one night. The development of increasingly advanced tourism has resulted in the development of Bali having many tourist villages which have been developed into attractive tourist destinations to visit. Several tourist villages in Bali, such as Penglipuran Village, Bangli, one of them are one of the cleanest villages in the world, causing this village to become the target of tourists to be able to visit and get to know their culture when visiting Bali. Based on tourism in Penglipuran Village which an impact on the impacts has caused by social, cultural, economic and environmental impacts, it can be seen that the highest average occurs in the environment (Arismayanti and Suwena, 2022). A part from being the cleanest village in the world, Bali also

has a cultural heritage in the form of rice terraces called ‘subak’ which are well known to foreign countries and have become a world cultural heritage, which is located in Jatiluwih Tourism Village. Jatiluwih Village is a village located in Penebel District, Tabanan Regency in Province Bali. This village is located on a plateau which causes this village have beautiful weather. Jatiluwih Village is a destination that has received recognition from UNESCO as one of the cultural heritages in Indonesia. Jatiluwih Village presents the beauty of nature, culture, and man-made tourist attractions. One of the tourism assets in Jatiluwih Village is the rice field irrigation system which is spread over 300 ha, which makes this village worthy of being called ‘the Culture Landscape Bali Province: The Subak System as Manifestation of The Tri Hita Karana Philosophy’ which means in The Indonesian language explains that Jatiluwih Village has a wealth of subak systems which are run on the basis of the local wisdom philosophy of Tri Hita Karana which consists of harmony between humans and others, humans and God, and humans and the environment (nature) (Bali Regional Regulation, 2012; Arismayanti and Rahyuda, 2022). So that the embodiment implemented through this subak system can be likened to representing the landscape culture in the Province of Bali.

In addition to the beauty of the agricultural system, Jatiluwih Tourism Village has a variety of tourist attractions that can attract tourists to come and visit such as nature tourism in the form of beautiful terraces, beautiful forests to waterfall tours which have been used as trekking, hiking and cycling tours. The second is in the form of cultural tourism, Jatiluwih Tourism Village has a culture in the form of agricultural rituals carried out before and after harvest which presents a sacred and authentic feel and there is also a cultural heritage in the form of temples to various traditions and rituals carried out by the people. Apart from that, tourist attractions that can be done in the Jatiluwih Tourism Village are in the form of attractions making typical snacks to making special souvenirs from Jatiluwih.

Jatiluwih Tourism Village has had an increase in tourist visits since it was designated as a world cultural heritage, because from year to year tourist visits always increase in balance with the natural beauty, culture and traditions that this tourist village has. Based on data from the village regarding tourist visits coming to Jatiluwih Tourism Village from 2015-2019 there has always been an increase. From 2015-2016 it increased by 29.90% or 49,143 people, in 2016-2017 it increased by 17.55% or 37,464 people, in 2017-2018 it increased by 10.45% or 26,216 people, in 2018-2019 it increased by 13.44% or 37,254 people. But unfortunately, because in 2020 there was a pandemic, tourist visits decreased until 2021. The beauty of the natural charm possessed by the Jatiluwih Tourism Village has caused tourists to be interested in visiting this tourist village. The village system is directed and well-organized with mutual support in village development. This village is advanced in its tourism development. The good management of the village from the community system, the subak system has led to the interest of researchers to study more deeply regarding the system owned by Jatiluwih Village. This study aims to examine the contribution of Jatiluwih Village as a tourist village and also examine the management system of Jatiluwih Tourism Village based on stakeholder collaboration. That way it can become a guideline for other tourist villages that are still developing to become successful tourist villages as tourist destinations in Bali.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various studies related to the management of tourist villages and also research related to Jatiluwih Village are presented in this article which can support this research such as research from According to Dewi (2013), Widari (2015), and Susila (2019) related to development of the Jatiluwih Tourism Village. According to Dewi (2013) explained that the government has a big role in the development of Jatiluwih Village even though the local government is only expected to act as a facilitator, so that the community's role is still minimal so it is expected that the local community needs a maximum role to participate in development. Tourism that prioritizes the participation of the local community. Widari (2015) explained that after the establishment of subak as a cultural heritage caused many good changes such as shifting the rice field plowing tools from buffalo to contractors, the preservation of agricultural traditions was maintained and carried out well, from the community it went well such as social organizations, more jobs enough, up to income and investment.

Community participation in the development of Jatiluwih Village has played an active role well, but the provision of information, comfort and provision of public facilities has not been very good, so there needs to be active support from the government to increase community participation. In addition, Widari (2021) reveals that the impact of subak management on the environment, such as a decrease in water resources to pollution caused by tourism businesses, the formation of inappropriate tourism facilities results in the loss of existing landscapes. In addition, there are also many positive impacts such as a clean and maintained environment, the existence of flora and fauna is also maintained, and awig-awig is also well maintained. Susila (2019) explained that the World Cultural Heritage of Jatiluwih Subak has a top-down policy, meaning that the policy is still experiencing a dilemma when implementing the policy in the field, besides that there is also a process that expands Jatiluwih Subak to become global.

Research related to the management of tourist villages was also researched by Andriani and Sunarta (2015), Junaid and Salim (2019), and by Paskasari (2020). Management of tourist villages according to Andriani and Sunarta (2015) explains that in the management of sustainable tourist villages using 6 (six) aspects such as organizational, financial, marketing, production and operations aspects. Aspects of Human Resources (HR), and management information systems. To create sustainable tourism, of course, it is necessary to maintain a good tourism environment, preserve nature and protect the existing ancestral cultural heritage. Apart from that, tourism managers certainly need to maintain and improve a good tourism management system such as maintaining and adding to existing infrastructure to improve the quality of existing human resources so that later it will create an integrated and sustainable tourism village. With various sources of relevant articles, of course, this will be able to support this research in the development of the Jatiluwih Tourism Village in the tourism village management system in the Jatiluwih Tourism Village. Young people who are active in making attractive tour packages for tourists who will visit. In addition, the role of Tourism Awareness Group (Kelompok Sadar Wisata/Pokdarwis) also has an active role in providing education and outreach to local communities to develop tourism in their tourist villages with community-based tourism. Paskasari (2020) explained that the management capacity of existing tourism

villages was studied using aspects of strategic leadership, program and process management as well as networking and also stakeholder relations which were found to be still not good because there was still no integrated management between the community and the government so as to create good tourism and according to what is desired.

3. METHOD AND THEORY

The method used in this study is a qualitative descriptive method, namely explaining the results of research related to the Jatiluwih Tourism Village management system based on collaboration between stakeholders obtained from interviews with the village head and also from presentation results from the Jatiluwih village head and obtained from the results of direct observation to the Tourism Village Jatiluwih. The theory used in this article is participation. Participation means the involvement of several parties to develop and succeed in the goals to be achieved. According to Ericson (in Slamet, 2003) explains that participation is the involvement of a person or many people in developing a strategy or plan to achieve a common goal. Meanwhile, according to Pitana (2002) states that participation is not only about the contribution of energy, time, and material but as an active involvement through a process that is maximized. Community participation is needed in the development of tourist destinations. The community as one of the stakeholders, community participation can be in the form of synergy between the community, the tourism service industry, and the government (Hulu et al., 2019). Community participation in the development of tourist destinations is involved in decision making at every stage, from planning, implementation, supervision and maintenance. The community is not only an object but also a subject in the development of tourist destinations (Suartha et al., 2022). One of them in this study, with the participation of the community and stakeholders in Jatiluwih Tourism Village is able to move existing tourism and also create superior tourism in the eyes of the world with guidelines from UNESCO as a cultural heritage in the world.

Managers in the tourism industry sector cannot be separated from the role of stakeholders in the process of managing tourist destinations. There are 5 (five) actors who have an active contribution and have an important role in the development and management of the tourism sector known as Pentahelix Stakeholders (Kagungan et al., 2022), such as: 1) Government, has the task of making rules and regulations that can maximize the potential of destinations tourism; 2) Academics and the institutions, play an important role in providing academic studies in supporting the development of tourist destinations; 3) The private sector, has a role in investing and bridging business activities in the tourism sector; 4) Local community (community) as subjects and objects in the development of the tourism industry in a destination and become operational both directly and indirectly in decision making; and 5) Media, has an important role in the context of marketing tourist destinations.

Community-Based Tourism (CBT) is an integrated approach or as a collaborative tool to fulfill socio-economic aspects by empowering communities through developing and marketing the potential of natural resources and community culture to provide visiting experiences for domestic and foreign tourists while increasing community participation (Dominique et al.,

2021). Tourism development through community-based tourism is not only limited to community involvement in tourism activities, but also related to better development of human resources (community) through socio-cultural, economic and environmental benefits (Gohori and Van der Merwe, 2020).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Jatiluwih Tourism Village is an area of 22.3 km² this village who has been managed very well, not only by village service elements but also by 5 (five) elements that are considered as the tourism potential management agency for Jatiluwih Village. Through a cooperation agreement that has been agreed upon by the five parties, namely: Tabanan Regency Government, Jatiluwih Service Village, Village Traditional Village, Gunungsari Traditional Village Element, and Jatiluwih Subak. These five elements are declared as the management body which directly oversees operational management that regulates the course of tourism activities in Jatiluwih Village. The tasks of the Jatiluwih Tourism Village Management Agency are as follows:

- 1). Develop and establish policies related to destination management;
- 2). Establish programs and operational work plans;
- 3). Establish operational budgets and expenditures;
- 4). Establish operational management;
- 5). Control and evaluate management performance operational; and also;
- 6). Reporting the accountability of the management body to the community.

Referring to the duties of the Jatiluwih Tourism Village Management Agency, the following can be seen as follows (Figure 1):

Figure 1: Structure of Jatiluwih Tourism Village Management Agency

Source: Jatiluwih Tourism Village (2022).

The structure of the Jatiluwih Village management operational management structure which has more complex activities as can be seen from the 2022 operational management structure as shown in chart 2 below:

Figure 2: Operational Management Structure Jatiluwih Tourism Village

Source: Jatiluwih Tourism Village (2022).

The duties of the operational management are as follows: 1) Carry out operational activities related to destination activities; 2) Develop a work program in the management sector which includes operational development and promotion; 3) Carry out policies and tasks assigned by the management; 4) Control the implementation of the program work; 5) Appointing the workforce needed in operational management; 6) Reporting the results of performance implementation to the management. The management which consists of five elements has outlined several important matters in the Cooperation Agreement including those related to: 1) Management Jatiluwih Tourism Village area; 2) Development of Jatiluwih Tourism Village area; 3) Fulfilment of rights and obligations; 4) Organizing; and 5) Profit distribution. The following data on tourist arrivals who came to visit the Jatiluwih Tourism Village in 2014-2021 which can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Jatiluwih Tourism Village Traveller Statistic

Source: Jatiluwih Tourism Village (2022).

The results of the large number of tourist visits per day reached 1,500 per day in 2019. Conditions prior to the Covid-19 pandemic had stimulated the wheels of the economy in the village because it opened up business opportunities for people in Jatiluwih Tourism Village. Businesses that are present in the community such as businesses providing accommodation in the form of homestays and hotels totalling 13 types of businesses until 2022 and there are 20 restaurants spread around the village area. The level of visits in 2020 has indeed decreased because in 2019 the total number of visits by Indonesian citizens (blue colour) and foreigners (orange colour) reached 314,443 tourists, while in 2020 it decreased to 93,743 and in 2021 there was a further decline to 52,804. So when presented from 2019 - 2020 the decline occurred by 70.19% and 2020-2021 by 43.67%.

Village income is also obtained from the sale of entrance tickets and parking tickets. Total income from reducing operational costs by 65% with details of 35% operational management costs, 12% development costs, 8% promotion costs and 10% management agency costs. The allocation of these five costs includes insurance costs for visitors who are covered in purchasing entrance tickets for tourists. The total net income each year has been divided into two major allocations, namely for the Jatiluwih Village as much as 55% and for the Regional Government as much as 45% which goes into the regional treasury. Of the 55% intended for Jatiluwih Village for contributing to the various elements involved in maintaining the destination in the form of rice fields, the 55% income is redistributed to 6 (six) elements based on the respective percentages that have been mutually agreed upon, namely:

- 1) Village elements Jatiluwih Service (15%);
- 2) Traditional Village Elements Jatiluwih Village (33%);
- 3) Gunungsari Traditional Village Elements (22%);
- 4) Jatiluwih Subak (26%);
- 5) Subak Abian Jatiluwih (2%); and
- 6) Subak Abian Gunungsari (2%).

Regarding this distribution, the Head of the Jati Luwih Tourism Village said:

“We still hope that later the percentage distribution of income for us to distribute to the village can be given even higher” (I Nengah Kartika S.Sos / October 2022).

Quoting from the expectations of the village head reflects that village elements still need an increase in income for their village community. He also mentioned that the use of incoming funds was also intended for a variety of social activities including:

- 1) Allotment of Social Funds for Temples and Catur Angga Batukau;
- 2) Death contribution;
- 3) Health aspect contribution;
- 4) Education Fund; and

5) Fertilizer Subsidy.

Utilization of the results of tourism activities is in line with what was stated by Borley, L. (1996) that tourism activities must be able to provide benefits, so that sustainable management is needed to preserve cultural heritage.

Jatiluwih Tourism Village Management Module

Management in the Jatiluwih Tourism Village can be seen in Figure 4. The following explains the 4C concept.

Figure 4: Module for Jatiluwih Tourism Village

Source: Processed by Researchers (2021).

It can be understood that the 4C concept has made Jatiluwih Tourism Village a well-developed village in managing its village, so that the government, villages, traditional villages, and subak cooperate well with each other. The 4C concept explains the concepts in the form of communication, contribution, collaboration and also commitment between stakeholders and villages so as to create a prosperous village. Mutual communication between the local government and traditional villages as well as official villages creates mutual trust and mutual understanding of what needs to be improved in the village and also what needs to be improved in village development. Then there are also good contributions, collaborations and commitments between the Jatiluwih service villages, Jatiluwih Subak, Gunungsari customary villages and also Jatiluwih Subak Subak so that they can increase village progress and also existing tourism progress.

Determination of Jatiluwih tourist destinations as a world cultural heritage (The World Heritage Site) affects the existence of Jatiluwih as a tourist destination. Tourism is a meeting system between hosts (host) and guests (guests). So that it directly or indirectly affects the interaction of Jatiluwih Subak with tourism. The interactions are formed, namely associative impacts and dissociative impacts (Putri et al., 2017):

- 1) Associative impacts, including, there is a symbiotic mutualism between subak and the tourism industry that runs in the Jatiluwih tourist destination. Tourist ticket fees provide benefits for subak, such as contributions to religious activities, and priority for providing fertilizer to maintain the existence of the iconic rice fields as one of the attributes of the Jatiluwih tourist destination, so that this associative impact is mutually beneficial.
- 2) Dissociative impacts, including tourism activities that threaten the existence of subak, such as waste management, disposal of waste due to tourism industry activities in the Jatiluwih area, such as restaurants and other places to eat. Overlapping related to cleaning irrigation canals is still experiencing problems between subak and other communities both in the Jatiluwih area and supporting areas.

Marketing Segment in Jatiluwih Tourism Village

Marketing is an activity to introduce the product you want to sell, with product marketing it will be easier to be known by the general public or consumers you want to target. Likewise, with tourist destinations, it is very important to be marketed so that tourists can be known so they can decide to visit. For marketing activities, Jatiluwih Village has a website and several social media intended to maximize the marketing of Jatiluwih Tourism Village which can be found at: Website address: www.jatiluwih.id. Other social media such as: Facebook: Jatiluwih Rice terrace; Instagram: @infojatiluwih; and YouTube: Jatiluwih Rice terrace. In addition to online social media, marketing from the Jatiluwih Tourism Village is also balanced with the distribution of printed media in the form of brochures or flyers and the installation of billboards in strategic places. Jatiluwih Tourism Village besides being a tourist attraction that attracts tourists to visit and enjoy the beauty of nature, culture, traditions, this village is also used as a field comparative study by several researchers, tour managers, students and the general public because Jatiluwih Tourism Village. This has succeeded in developing the village to become a superior village, and successful in managing the tourism objects that are owned, both from their nature to their culture and traditions. So it's not surprising that many of these villages use research as a comparison for the development of villages in other areas to be successful and develop properly that can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Photo of a Field Comparative Study Visit

Source: Researcher, 2022.

The marketing strategy for the Jatiluwih tourist destination is through the Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning. Segmenting Jatiluwih tourist destinations based on four market segmentation variables, covering: 1) Geographic variables, the dominant age group visiting Jatiluwih tourist destinations is the 21-30 year old group, dominated by students and undergraduates; 2) Demographic variable, dominated by domestic tourists, followed by foreign tourists (Australia and England); 3) Psychographic variables, tourists visiting the background are the natural beauty of Jatiluwih, dominated by repeater guests; 4) Consumer Behaviour Variable, as for aspects of behaviour at Jatiluwih tourist destinations, it can be seen from the activities of tourists who spend one to two hours, the amount of money spent at Jatiluwih tourist destinations is between Rp. 50,000 to Rp. 100,000. Targeting is a strategy to determine the market based on segments that have been identified. Positioning is the process of placing the attributes of the Jatiluwih tourist destination in the minds of tourists and giving an impression, thereby influencing tourists' decisions to visit (Utama and Suyasa, 2018). To be able to target the intended market segment, a collaboration of all stakeholders is needed in advancing tourist destinations, this is in line with the results of Haribawa and Arif (2017) study which examined Stakeholder Orientation Analysis for Ecotourism Development. The Pentahelix stakeholder components in the Jatiluwih tourist destination are as follows:

Table 1: Stakeholder Orientation Analysis for Ecotourism Development

Component	Observation List Result
Government	Tabanan Regency Government in the management of Tourist Destinations by forming a management body for the Jatiluwih tourist destination.
Private sector	Investments support tourism activities in the Jatiluwih Tourism Village such as accommodation and food and drink service providers in the Jatiluwih.
Community	Investments support tourism activities in the Jatiluwih Tourism Village such as accommodation and food and drink service providers in the Jatiluwih.
Academic	The role of academics through the presence of educational institutions to carry out research, community service and provide assistance and provide studies in providing supplements to every decision taken by the manager of the Jatiluwih tourist destination. One example is training for Jatiluwih Tourism Village managers, homestay management training that has the principles of sustainable tourism.
Media	Promoting Jatiluwih Tourism Village with various platforms such as the Jatiluwih article contained in the Bali Bible, and Now Bali, as one of the influential tourism promotion media platforms, as well as through YouTube and Instagram social media platforms.

Source: Researcher, 2022.

Based on the results of the observations and interviews above, the ideal 'Pentahelix stakeholder' collaboration strategy that can be carried out in Jatiluwih Tourism Village is as follows:

Table 2: IFAS Strategic Factors of Pentahelix Stakeholder' Collaboration

IFAS	Strategic Factor	Weight	Rating	Score
Strengths	There is already a tourism potential management agency for Jatiluwih Village (5 elements)	0.09	4	0.34
	UNESCO world heritage site	0.09	5	0.43
	The beauty of rice terrace tourist attraction	0.09	5	0.43
	Culture and tradition	0.06	4	0.23
	Tourism village role model	0.06	4	0.23
	Operational management team work	0.06	4	0.23
	There are 13 types of hotel businesses and 20 restaurants owned by local communities	0.06	4	0.23
	Local wisdom	0.09	5	0.43
	Red line track (Barack Obama trekking path)	0.09	5	0.43
Total Score of Strength				2.97
Weaknesses	Profit sharing (not ideal profit sharing)	0.09	2.9	0.25
	Utilization of social media platforms for promotion	0.09	2	0.17
	Existence of farmers	0.06	2	0.11
	Orientation of the tourism industry but opposite to preservation	0.06	2.5	0.14
	No planning, RDTR (Spatial Detailed Plan)	0.06	2	0.11
Total Score Weaknesses				0.79
Total Internal Factor Score		1.00		3.76

Source: Researcher, 2022.

As for the results of the identification of indicators that have been analysed based on the weight and rating of the results of interviews with key informants, the Internal Factor Analysis Strategy (IFAS) analysis results obtained on the strengths and weaknesses that can be maximized in managing the potential of Jatiluwih Tourism Village, the total score on the strength indicator with a value 2.97. While the value of weaknesses obtained a score of 0.79.

Table 3: EFAS Strategic Factors of Pentahelix Stakeholder' Collaboration

EFAS	Strategic Factor	Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunities	G20 Event (delegation visited Jatiluwih Tourism Village)	0.14	5	0.71
	Based tourism village marketing	0.14	4	0.57
	Jatiluwih Festival	0.14	4	0.57
Total Opportunities Score				1.86
Threats	Ukraine versus Russia wars	0.14	2	0.29
	Land conversion due to the tourism industry (restaurant)	0.14	2.9	0.41
	Mass tourism in conservation areas	0.10	2	0.19
	Modernization amid world heritage status	0.10	2	0.19
	Global economic recession 2023	0.10	2	0.19
Total Score Threats				1.27
Total Score External Factors		1.00		3.13

Source: Researcher, 2022.

The results of the identification of indicators that have been analysed based on the weight and rating of the results of interviews with key informants, obtained the value / score of the External

Factor Analysis Strategy (EFAS) analysis on opportunities and threats that can be maximized in managing the potential of Jatiluwih as tourist village, so the total score on the opportunities indicators) with a value of 1.86. While the value of threats obtained a score of 1.27.

To formulate an ideal strategy that can be carried out in the “Pentahelix stakeholder” based on Jatiluwih Tourism Village potential management system, namely by looking at the internal factor analysis strategy (IFAS) coordinates with the X coordinates and the External Factor Analysis Strategy (EFAS) with the Y coordinates. Each coordinate is obtained by the following calculation, $X = (SW)/2$ and Y coordinate = $(X)/2$, then the value is obtained, X coordinate = $(2.18)/2$, $X = 1.09$. While the coordinate value $Y = (0.59)/2$, then $Y = 0.29$.

Figure 6: Strategic Factors of Pentahelix Stakeholder’ Collaboration Quadrant

Based on these results, the ideal strategy for managing the Jatiluwih, namely $X = 1.09$ and $Y = 0.29$, is in Quadrant I, namely the SO (strength-opportunity)

Figure 7: Pentahelix Stakeholder’ Collaboration Quadrant based on Jatiluwih Tourism Village Potential Management System

Based on the IFAS and EFAS analysis diagrams, the potential strategy coordinate points are in quadrant I, namely supporting an aggressive strategy. Based on this analysis, the ideal strategy that can be applied in collaboration-based management with Pentahelix stakeholders is as follows:

The role of the Government, the strategy in Quadrant I that can be carried out is to maintain by paying attention to the Jatiluwih tourist village development strategy by not threatening the status of the world heritage site by UNESCO and form a special team to ensure that the values of the world heritage site status that must be maintained are not violated or ignored. Making binding regulations to protect the Jatiluwih tourist village supporting areas, such as paying attention to the community in the Jatiluwih tourist village supporting areas so that they participate in protecting especially the environmental aspects and not converting land massively which can have an impact both directly and indirectly on Jatiluwih Tourism Village.

The role of the Private Sector, the strategy in Quadrant I that can be carried out is first, can carry out training as a form of Corporate Social Responsibility in the form of service standards or sequences of service in 13 types of guest accommodation businesses (homestays and guest houses) and 20 types of restaurant businesses owned by the community local.

The role of the Community, the strategy in Quadrant I can be maximized as first, the existence of the subak organization acts as the main object and subject in maintaining the status of The world heritage site from UNESCO, by still paying attention to the values of the Tri Hita Karana philosophy as the basis for maintaining activities subak which has been recognized by UNESCO.

The role of Academic (academics and educational and research institutions), the strategy in Quadrant I can be maximized through, firstly carrying out community service with supporting activities targeting the community in Jatiluwih and buffer zones, secondly playing an active role in creating science and technology innovations that can be applied in Jatiluwih to support tourism activities but not threaten the status of the world heritage site.

The role Media, while the strategy in quadrant I that can be carried out is as follows carry out marketing effort activities to target market shares that are in accordance with the Jatiluwih tourist attraction which prioritizes natural and cultural preservation rather than mass tourism, both media provide good imagery and education about the status of the Jatiluwih world heritage site as a tourist destination.

5. CONCLUSION

Jatiluwih Tourism Village is a cultural heritage that has been established by UNESCO and is a cultural heritage that represents the cultural landscape owned by the province of Bali which is based on the Tri Hita Karana philosophy, namely harmony between humans and humans, nature and the creator. Jatiluwih as tourist villages have great potential to create jobs, and new business opportunities for the creative economy, so that they can become an alternative to the resilience of the Jatiluwih community economy. To sustain this situation the collaboration every stakeholder should be as priority to keep sustainability in culture, social and economy.

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